

Effect of Sugars on the Inhibition of the Precipitation of Ceric Hydroxide from a Solution of Ceric Ammonium Nitrate.

BY M. V. NABAR AND MATA PRASAD.

Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 193), Mehrotra and Sen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 117), and Sen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 131), have studied the peptisation of various metallic hydroxides in the presence of sugars. They have determined the amount of sugar which is necessary to prevent the precipitation of the hydroxides by alkali. Patel and Desai (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 161), have studied the effect of non-electrolytes on the precipitation of thorium hydroxide from a solution of thorium nitrate by alkali. They find that sugars and glycerol alone are effective in preventing or inhibiting the precipitation. Nabar, Patel and Desai (*Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 57, 173), find that the inhibition of the precipitation of thorium hydroxide increases with an increase in the hydroxyl groups in sugars.

The present investigation deals with the study of the effect of non-electrolytes on the inhibition of the precipitation of ceric hydroxide from a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate from the viewpoint put forward by Nabar, Patel and Desai (*loc. cit.*). The peptisation of ceric hydroxide from ceric chloride by sugars has already been studied by Mehrotra and Sen (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

An approximately $M/40$ solution of ceric ammonium nitrate (B. D. H.) was prepared and its concentration was accurately determined. A solution of Merck's extra pure caustic soda was prepared, standardised and stocked in a Jena-glass flask. The non-electrolytes used were (1) ethylene glycol, (2) glycerol, (3) mannitol, (4) glucose, (5) lactose, (6) maltose, (7) sucrose, and (8) fructose.

A known volume of ceric ammonium nitrate was taken in a number of test tubes and the total volume was made up to 30 c.c. by adding different amounts of non-electrolytes and distilled water. 5 C.c.

of sodium hydroxide solution was taken in another set of test tubes ; the amount of NaOH in 5 c.c. was more than that required for the complete precipitation of cerium nitrate contained in the former set of test tubes. The contents of the two sets of tubes were then thoroughly mixed, the same mode of mixing being followed throughout the investigation. The amount of the non-electrolyte in the tube, in which the appearance of the precipitate is just prevented, is the minimum amount required to inhibit the precipitation of ceric hydroxide. Two series of such observations were taken and the mean of the two is given in all the following tables.

Effect of volume.—The effect of the change in the total volume of the mixture on the amount of sugars required to inhibit the precipitation of ceric hydroxide by a fixed amount of NaOH is given in Table I.

TABLE I.

NaOH in the mixture = 1.25 m. mols. Ceric ammonium nitrate = 0.05 m. mols.

Total volume.	Non-electrolytes required in m. mols.				
	Fructose.	Sucrose.	Maltose.	Lactose.	Glucose.
10 c. c.	0.98	0.061	0.225	0.525	2.15
20	0.064	0.058	0.156	0.406	1.5
30	0.048	0.054	0.119	0.35	1.25
40	0.048	0.054	0.119	0.35	1.25
50	0.048	0.054	0.119	0.35	1.25
60	0.048	0.054	0.119	0.35	1.25

It appears that with an increase in the total volume of the mixture, the amount of sugar required to inhibit the precipitation at first decreases and then reaches a constant value.

The clear liquid obtained in these mixtures was cataphoretically examined and was found to be a sol containing negatively charged particles. The formation of these particles is due to the adsorption of OH⁻ ions by ceric hydroxide in the presence of sugars which are also probably adsorbed to some extent by the colloidal particles. The decrease in the amount of sugars with an increase in the total volume is due to the stabilisation of the sol on dilution.

Effect of the amount of ceric ammonium nitrate.—The effect of the amount of the salt on the non-electrolytes required to inhibit the precipitation by a fixed amount of caustic soda (1.25 m. mols.) is given in Table II. The total volume of the mixture was 30 c.c.

TABLE II (A).

Ceric ammonium nitrate (in m. mols.).	Non-electrolytes required in m. mols..				
	Fructose.	Sucrose.	Maltose.	Lactose.	Glucose.
0.025	0.024	0.022	0.056	0.150	0.500
0.0375	0.034	0.033	0.088	0.250	0.800
0.05	0.048	0.054	0.119	0.350	1.250
0.0625	0.070	0.078	0.163	0.475	1.900
0.075	0.090	0.118	0.238	0.663	2.700
0.0875	0.130	0.150	0.338	—	4.100

TABLE II (B).

Ceric ammonium nitrate (in m. mols.)	...	0.0062	0.0125	0.0156	0.0187	0.025	0.0375
Mannitol (in m. mols.)	...	...	0.325	...	...	0.625	1.125
Glycerol	..	...	0.60	1.45	...	2.2	3.1
Ethylene glycol	.,	...	...	2	3.3	4.8	6.8

The tables show that the amount of non-electrolytes required is greater as the amount of salt in the mixture is increased. These results are similar to those obtained by Mehrotra and Sen (*loc. cit.*) in the peptisation of the ceric hydroxide. This increase in the amount of sugars is due to an increase in the number of colloidal particles of ceric hydroxide formed in a fixed volume of the mixture.

The inhibiting power of the non-electrolytes increases as, ethylene glycol < glycerol < mannitol < glucose < lactose < maltose < fructose < sucrose. This shows that the number of OH groups in the non-electrolyte influences its inhibiting power; cane sugar, maltose and lactose which contain eight OH groups are better inhibitors than glucose and fructose, glycerol and glycol which contain five, three and two OH groups respectively. The behaviour of fructose is anomalous as its

inhibiting power is more than that of sucrose which contains more OH groups than fructose. The ketone group in fructose may be responsible for this anomaly.

Effect of the amount of alkali.—The following table shows the effect of the addition of increasing amounts of alkali on the amount of the non-electrolyte required to inhibit the precipitation.

TABLE III.

Ceric ammonium nitrate=0.025 m. mols. Total vol.=30 c.c.

NaOH (in m. mols.).	Amount of non-electrolytes required in m. mols.					
	Fructose.	Sucrose.	Maltose.	Lactose.	Glucose.	Glycerol.
0.25	0.130	0.160	0.219	0.969	7.75	20.60
0.375	0.050	0.078	0.113	0.382	1.90	11.00
0.50	0.034	0.060	0.082	0.244	0.85	6.00
0.75	0.024	0.030	0.056	0.175	0.50	1.75
1.00	0.024	0.022	0.056	0.150	0.50	1.75
1.25	0.024	0.022	0.056	0.150	0.50	1.75

With an increase in the amount of alkali, the amount of non-electrolyte required to inhibit the precipitation at first decreases and then reaches a constant value.

Separate experiments showed that the non-electrolytes alone could not inhibit the precipitation of the hydroxide if the amount of the alkali added was not greater than that required for complete precipitation. The part played (by the excess of the hydroxyl ions) in the inhibition is indicated by the decrease in the amount of the non-electrolyte required to inhibit the precipitation and is due to the stabilising influence of these ions. But certain minimum amount of the non-electrolyte is also essential for causing the inhibition in precipitation; sodium hydroxide alone can not inhibit the formation of the precipitate. The decrease in the amount of the non-electrolytes required in the presence of increasing amount of NaOH may possibly be due to the suppression in the adsorption of the non-electrolyte by OH ions. Experiments on the adsorption of these non-electrolytes under conditions described above are necessary before any definite conclusion regarding the inhibition of the precipitation can be drawn.

Summary.

The effect of (1) change in total volume, (2) amount of salt and (3) amount of alkali on the inhibition of the precipitation of ceric hydroxide from ceric ammonium nitrate solution by non-electrolytes has been studied.

The amount of the non-electrolyte required for inhibiting the precipitation decreases with an increase in (1) the total volume, and (2) the amount of alkali in the mixture up to a certain limit and then reaches a constant value but it increases with an increase in the amount of cerium ions in the solution.

The inhibiting power of the non-electrolytes decreases as sucrose > fructose > maltose > lactose > glucose > mannitol > glycerol > glycol.

The effect of the excess of alkali and of the non-electrolytes on the inhibition of the precipitation is discussed.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY.

Received November 3, 1932.

